

MICROBES AND MICROBIOME

We humans are partly microbes. Over 100 trillion of them live on and inside our bodies. In fact, the number of microbes in an average human body is about the same as the number of human cells. Most of them can be found in our gut, particularly in the large intestine.

The human microbiome is a dynamic and interactive micro-ecosystem comprising diverse microorganisms and their interaction with the environment through metabolites, genes and other components within the human body. The composition of the human microbiome is unique in each individual, just like a fingerprint.

Human-microbe interplay is a major driver of health and well-being, and the profiling of microbiomes will be an essential feature of personalised preventive nutrition and precision medicine of the future.

CONTACT

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Dr. Joël Doré

France's National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE)

info@humanmicrobiomeaction.eu

COMMUNICATION CONTACT

Stephan Kampshoff

European Food Information Council (EUFIC)

comms@humanmicrobiomeaction.eu

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Sustainable Food System Network:
Microbiome Community

**Human
Microbiome
Action**

HUMAN MICROBIOME ACTION TOWARDS BETTER PUBLIC HEALTH

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OUR HISTORY

Human Microbiome Action is an EU-funded Horizon 2020 project that aims to maximise the impact of European microbiome research and innovation to tackle the epidemics of chronic diseases.

The project counts 17 partners from 9 European countries who work together to increase the impact of European microbiome research and innovation by ensuring coherence and harmony in the way microbiome research is and will be performed.

The project will last for 3 years (2021-2024) and is coordinated by France's National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE).

BACKGROUND

For the last decades, chronic diseases have been on the rise across the world, presenting a major threat to public health.

The human microbiome is increasingly recognized for its crucial role in maintaining health and well-being and particularly for the prevention and treatment of many non-communicable diseases. This knowledge requires us to rethink current health systems and include human-microbe interplay as a key element in the development of new preventive and therapeutic approaches.

OUR GOALS

- Bring together leading EU and international players to build a strong partnership and network.
- Map the current scientific state-of-play and identify gaps of knowledge.
- Develop international synergies for microbiome research and knowledge transfer.
- Identify and propose key actions required to achieve impact.

OUR ACTIVITIES

- Provide instruments to support robust usage of microbiome knowledge to tackle the epidemics of chronic diseases.
- Build consensus on the priorities and means as part of a roadmap for EU microbiome science and its translation.
- Develop a range of guidance documents and recommendations for researchers, public health officials and industry stakeholders to provide roadmaps for necessary foundations and key actions that allow for aligned microbiome research in the future.

BENEFITS OF THE PROJECT

The Human Microbiome Action project will benefit society, including improving health outcomes, advancing scientific knowledge, and promoting public awareness of the importance of the human microbiome.

"With the Human Microbiome Action Project, human microbiomes will be recognized for their true value to help secure the future of mankind"

GET INVOLVED IN THE PROJECT!

- **Join** the Stakeholder's Advisory Board and provide strategic advice from an external point of view and take part in the consensus-building process.
- **Raise** awareness about the importance of microbiome and join the **#MicrobiomeAmbassador** campaign on social media.
- **Participate** in outreach activities and educational programs.
- **Subscribe** to our newsletter.

